

Learning Management System Advancement with onCloud Based System

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Abstract

The widespread use of the internet has led to the adoption of new business models in many sectors. Companies like Grab in transportation and Airbnb in accommodation are growing rapidly, replacing traditional business models that did not rely on internet and technological advancements. Therefore, many industries are rapidly changing, and the education sector, which is responsible for preparing a skilled workforce, must find new ways to adapt to the changing times. In 2021, Panergayo reported that an enhanced Learning Management System could improve student self-efficacy and time management. Avram made technological statements in 2014, and Hassan in 2022, suggesting that cloud technology adoption can enhance productivity and effectiveness while significantly reducing system costs. The aim of this article is to provide a general perspective on how the onCloud Learning Management System can assist the education industry in adopting a new business model that meets the needs of the modern era.

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